

**EFFECTIVE METHODS OF CREATING JOBS AND ENSURING
EMPLOYMENT IN CORPORATE ENTERPRISES (IN THE CASE OF
BUKHARA REGION).**

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Eshov Azamat Bakhshilloevich

Asian International University.

M-5 group students Iqt 22

Annotate

In this article, in the process of scientific organization of labor, ways to achieve the full manifestation of the worker's ability to work, labor productivity and its indicators, state employment policy in the context of economic modernization, the level of employment and unemployment of the population in the conditions of economic modernization, the basics of formalizing labor relations in the digital economy, proposals and recommendations for improving labor legislation in our country.

Key words

Scientific organization of labor, labor process, employment policy, modernization, digital economy, real jobs, labor market, work collectives, outstaffing, freelancing, crowdsourcing.

The scientific organization of labor relies on the law of supply and demand, the law of value and 27 other laws, which are considered the most important laws of the market economy. Labor is organized by fulfilling requirements such as providing employment in accordance with the abilities and capabilities of each employee, rewarding and encouraging them in accordance with the quantity and quality of their work, competition in the use of employees, demand and supply, and taking into account the created consumer value. It is necessary to ensure a high level of labor productivity by achieving the full manifestation of the employee's work ability in the organization of work. The labor process carried out in enterprises largely depends on the technical and technological level of the enterprise. The methods of work on different machines differ from each other. It is of great importance that the work is organized in accordance with the tools in which it is carried out.

In the conditions of modernization of the economy, the state employment policy should be directed to the effective use of labor potential as a component of

the socio-economic development of the region and the solution of employment problems in terms of its development. In the conditions of economic renewal, employment and unemployment of the population can change rapidly. The labor market is of great importance in providing employment to the population and eliminating unemployment in the Bukhara region. Because in the region, the demand for labor force and its supply collide in the labor market. Therefore, effective development of this infrastructure is one of the main factors of socio-economic development in the region.

The level of employment of the population is one of the indicators representing the scale of development of the economy of any country.

Table-1

Fundamentals of formalizing labor relations in the digital economy.

Digital Uzbekistan-2023 strategy	2030-national goals and tasks in the field of sustainable development	Employment promotion strategy in 2021-2030	Innovative development strategy of Uzbekistan in 2022-2030	Development strategy of Uzbekistan until 2035
Building a digital economy and e-government	Increasing effective and decent employment	Expanding formal and sustainable employment	Developing human capital	High economic growth and formation of the middle class

According to the Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations of the Republic of Uzbekistan, their number is around 400-500 thousand people. According to these data, today there is a demand for about 2 million new jobs in the republic. The real jobs being created could not meet such a high demand. In the labor market, there will be no opportunity to achieve economic growth in the future if the balance between supply and demand for labor is not ensured. Therefore, extensive measures are being taken to improve the state policy in the labor market.

New approaches to the regulation of the labor market in the country, in particular, encouraging entrepreneurship and employers, self-employment, vocational training of the unemployed, improving skills, taking into account work experience increased attention to the use of information systems.

According to the new legislation on providing employment to the population, for the first time, the legal basis of the activity of employers providing outstaffing services was established. Outstaffing was defined as a type of services provided by the employer by temporarily sending its employees to other legal entities with their

consent to perform the labor tasks specified in the labor contracts concluded between the employer and its employee, collective agreements.

In accordance with the contract on the provision of outstaffing services, employees perform their work duties under the management and control of the legal entity to which they are sent by the employer, in the interests of that legal entity. The payment of wages for the work of employees is carried out by the employer.

Self-employed persons who provide services (doing work) via the Internet are considered freelancers. They provide services to foreign individuals and legal entities without entering into a contract by accepting a public offer on a transaction (offerta) or exchanging electronic messages or placing invoices (invoices), including in electronic form has the right to (do things).

Loans from the State Fund for Employment Assistance will be allocated to organizations that have received an order to create workplaces. The loan is granted in national currency for a period of up to 3 years and is set up to 50 times the basic calculation amount for one job. The number of services provided to jobseekers and unemployed persons applying to local labor authorities has been increased from 7 to 16.

Vocational training, retraining and improvement of the skills of unemployed persons and persons looking for work was defined as one of the main directions of the state policy in the field of employment of the population. Persons in need of social protection, who have difficulty finding a job and cannot compete on equal terms in the labor market, have received additional guarantees for employment.

The amount of unemployment benefit has been increased by 2.5 times. It was established that unemployment benefits for all categories of unemployed persons will be paid for 26 calendar weeks (previously it was 13 calendar weeks) within a 12-month period. During the period of vocational training, retraining or professional development, unemployment benefits will be paid for up to 26 calendar weeks at the expense of the State Employment Assistance Fund. The amount of pensions has been increased to 2-2.5 times.

In order to stimulate employment and attract the population to entrepreneurship, a subsidy was allocated to employers from the funds of the State Employment Support Fund.

Subsidies are one and a half of the minimum wage for each employee for six months to compensate employers for training, retraining or upgrading the skills of employees hired on the referral of local labor authorities. is allocated in the amount up to.

Jobseekers and unemployed persons, citizens returning from labor migration, women from low-income families, managers and employees of farms, managers and members of farms, farm land are admitted to vocational training centers. Grants are allocated to the organization and "master-apprentice" schools for vocational training, re-training and upgrading of their qualifications, as well as training in the production itself.

According to the analysis, the indicator of economic activity and employment among women is about 2 times lower than that of men, and it is more than 2 times higher among rural residents.

Table-2

Level of economic activity and employment of urban and rural population in Bukhara region, %⁴

Indicators	Economic activity		Employment	
	men of the population	of women of the population	men of the population	of women of the population
villagers	74,2	27,5	62,8	22,3
city residents	73,5	38,7	61,3	34,5

234,000 of the unemployed in our region are women. Economic activity among women is low compared to men, and the average level of economic activity among women in the last 5 years was 50.0%. For example, in the last 5 years, the level of economic activity of women in the region was on average 65.0%. At the same time, 76.0% of able-bodied men were economically active, had a job or were actively looking for a job. In our province, this indicator was 48.0% among women and 65.0% among men. According to statistical data, the economic activity of women in our republic is low compared to the indicators of other transition economy countries and the world average.

Taking this into account, special attention is paid to providing women with decent work, preparing them for professions and improving their qualifications.

For this purpose, funds equivalent to 2 million US dollars of the Reconstruction and Development Fund were directed to microfinance service organizations and non-governmental non-profit organizations to support projects involving young people and women in small business.

⁴ file:///C:/Users/user/Downloads/DEMOGRAFIK%20HOLAT%20(1).pdf

With the support of women's and girls' committees of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regions and the city of Tashkent, women's entrepreneurship centers with the status of non-governmental non-profit organizations were established. In order to direct women to national crafts (goldsmithing, embroidery, carpet weaving), they have started to attach them to local masters-craftsmen according to the "master-apprentice" tradition and train them in the trade. is being placed.

Also, the "road map" has been developed by the Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations to ensure the employment and placement of housewives who intend to work according to their specialties and is being consistently implemented. The "Women's Book" is being implemented in the neighborhood to work with the unemployed, single mothers and women with problems.

In the Bukhara region, women are being provided with work by establishing the activity of handicraft and silk production clusters. For this purpose, light construction workshops specializing in handicrafts and silk production are being established in the neighborhoods.

Today, more than 200 million people are unemployed worldwide, 35% of them are young people. The unemployment rate among young people is 2-3 times higher than that of older people.

This situation is clearly reflected in the dynamics of GDP and youth employment around the world. Despite the decrease in the level of poverty in the world, in many countries it is possible to include young people in the poor population.

As a result of changes in the labor market, "flexible labor" is widespread, as a result of which part-time and short-term labor contracts are increasing, especially among young people. We can conclude from this that, firstly, mobility among young people, and secondly, the lack of protection of young people in the labor market is increasing, and the opportunity to engage in work on the basis of a full-time employment contract is limited. As a result, many young people are employed in seasonal, temporary jobs and are forced to provide self-employment.

According to the data of 2022, the majority of young men in our republic were employed in construction (36.0%) and in the service sector (2.0%). At the same time, the share of employees in public administration and trade has also increased. In turn, the share of agriculture has sharply decreased (from 45.0% to 7.0%), which indicates that the migration of young people to cities is increasing. The majority of women among young people are in state enterprises (36.0%), in the service sector

(27.0%) and in industry (20.0%). Women's employment in agriculture has also sharply decreased.

According to the analyzes carried out in the labor market, the share of informally employed people among 16-24-year-olds in 2022 was 34.0%. Compared to 2006, this indicator has improved.

Among young people, men are more likely to work on the basis of informal labor contracts than women. In 2022, 44.0% of 18-24-year-old men, 44.0% of women and 21.0% of women were in the informal sector. Informal contracts are more common among rural youth than urban youth. It should be noted that informal employment contracts are rare among young people with higher education.

In order to improve the efficiency of labor bodies:

a) it is necessary to implement further organizational and legal measures to optimize the goals, tasks, functions, organizational structure, number of employees, and payment for their work of labor bodies;

b) decentralized employment policy by the state, delegation of some functions of the MHLTO of the Republic of Uzbekistan, how to develop and implement job creation programs, transfer sample surveys of the labor force and forecasts of the situation in the labor market, etc., regional EPC, including fiscal decentralization, expanding the income and expenditure base of regional offices of the Employment Support Fund;

c) improvement of the system of public services (introduction of uniform principles of recruitment, promotion, qualification improvement and retraining of civil servants) in general, state bodies, including labor bodies.

d) introduction of modern forms of outsourcing, crowdsourcing, PPP in the activities of labor bodies;

e) to strengthen public control and increase the transparency of the activities of local labor bodies.

Using the above analysis, we would like to make the following recommendations regarding the development and improvement of the level of employment in Bukhara region.

Residents of our region have been effectively using various business methods for developing their own business, handicrafts, homemaking, and various business methods since ancient times. Therefore, based on foreign experience, it is appropriate to use crowdsourcing and crowdfunding technologies, which are one of the modern innovations in the region.⁵

⁵ <https://telegra.ph/KRAUDSORSING-NIMA-yohud-uning-shahsij-biznesni-tashkil-ehlishdagi-yrni-02-26>

The meaning of crowdsourcing (from the English crowdsourcing, crowd - "mass" and sourcing - "resource use") is to solve problems and create new brands based on the creativity, experience and knowledge of ordinary people. With the help of crowdsourcing technology, it is possible to find solutions to business, social and political problems using human resources. For the first time, in 2003, Louis von Ahn, together with his team, put into practice the concept of Crowdsourcing, which means that things that cannot be done by computers can be done easily and quickly by a team. Later, in 2006, Wired magazine reporter Jeff Howe defined this concept in his article entitled "The Rise of Crowdsourcing". This is how Crowdsourcing is applied to the public.

But, like the sun rising from the east, in our country with a rich heritage, Crowdsourcing is formed at the core of our values that have become a tradition since time immemorial, that is, in common people's language, a bug. In the national festivals, everyone unites towards one goal, i.e. to clean up the environment and protect nature. The main purpose of crowdsourcing technology is to solve the existing problem together. ⁶

Table-3

Advantages of crowdsourcing

Advantages of crowdsourcing	The essence of the advantage of crowdsourcing
The formation of a large area	In other words, it is possible for a group of people from different fields and with different views to unite over one problem.
Availability of user engagement	In this case, there is a high possibility of attracting users by sharing ideas, discussing the result of work and telling friends about the project.
Availability of a large selection	Gives the customer a choice. For one product, it will be possible to choose the most suitable one among the projects of people living in different parts of the world with different experiences, different professions and views, different nationalities and religions.
Purchase of the product	By choosing a product that has been chosen by many, or rather, already has a buyer, you know the opinion of the public and ensure that your product will be bought in the

⁶ <https://telegra.ph/KRAUDSORSING-NIMA-yohud-uning-shahsij-biznesni-tashkil-ehitshdagi-yrni-02-26>

	future.
A waste of time	A solution to the problem is found with great interest in a very short period of time.
Spend less money	You won't spend a lot of money on it. Of course, the winner whose idea is approved will receive the promised amount. But it won't cost too much.
Young people and people with disabilities will be able to test their talent	For example, Crowdsourcing opens the door to opportunities for young people who are a good designer, architect, poet, and creative person in remote regions and districts.

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